

Synthesis and application of 2-nitro-2',4'-dihydroxyazobenzene, 4-nitro-2',4'-dihydroxyazobenzene and 2-carboxy-2'-hydroxyazonaphthol for dyeing of jute fabric

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Abstract : The following three azo dyes namely, 2-nitro-2',4'-dihydroxyazobenzene (I), 4-Nitro-2',4'-dihydroxyazobenzene (II) and 2-carboxy-2'-hydroxyazonaphthol (III) have been synthesized and characterized. These three azo dyes have been successfully applied for dyeing of bleached jute fabric in alkaline medium following the conventional exhaust method. The performance of the dyes are evaluated by evaluating the colour yield and wash fastness of the dyed fabric samples.

Keywords : Jute fabric, bleaching, dyeing, azo dye, dye exhaustion.

The emergence of diverse classes of synthetic dyes including azo dyes occurred due to constant efforts to find specific dye or a particular class of dye for application on diverse materials of industrial importance¹ viz. jute, aluminium sheet, leather, wool etc. Out of different classes of dyes, azo dyes cover a major area due to their simplicity of synthesis and applicability of different materials in industries. Jute, an important biodegradable fibre, has created renewed interest due to its application to decorative and value added products. So the wet processing of jute has occupied a very important position in jute industry as the diversified products need good look and attractive feel where bleaching, dyeing, finishing etc. of jute is a must. A number of work has been carried out in the field of bleaching, dyeing etc. like energy saving ambient temperature bleaching, simultaneous operation of several processes, reuse of bleach as well as dye bath, bleaching with different agents, dyeing with several class of dyes etc.¹. Due to these effects jute products with attractive look can be made with different option and processes of the products with bright shade. Thus improvement of feel of the jute product and colouration of jute fibre by means of dyeing or printing is must¹.

Considering the fastness and brilliancy of shades, use of azo dyes for dyeing of jute fabric herald a new era in dyeing industry. We can go for vat or reactive dyeing on hydrogen peroxide bleached fabric. But for the production of cheap products with moderate to low fastness properties we go for acid, basic, direct dyes etc., so the product can be produced depending on the end use requirement. Mostly the dyes

suitable for cellulosic fibre dyeing are used for dyeing of jute with process and method modification. In the present work three different azo dyes namely, 2-nitro-2',4'-dihydroxyazobenzene (I), 4-nitro-2',4'-dihydroxyazobenzene (II) and 2-carboxy-2'-hydroxyazonaphthol (III) have been synthesized and applied on jute fabric by conventional exhaust method in alkaline medium. All the synthesized dyes have azo group as chromophore and dye I and II have two hydroxy groups and a nitro group as auxochrome and dye III has carboxy and hydroxy groups as auxochrome. The dyes have been characterized and the performance of dyed jute fabric samples have been evaluated.

Experimental

Fabric :

A plain weave grey jute fabric having following specification was used; Warp : 65 ends/dm (count, 152 tex); Weft : 71 ends/dm (count, 160 tex); Fabric mass ; 220 g/sq. m (at 65% RH and 30 °C).

Chemicals :

The following analytical grade chemicals (purity around 99%) from S. D. Fine-chem Limited were used for the preparation of dyes I, II and III : *o*-nitroaniline, *p*-nitroaniline, resorcinol, anthranilic acid, β -naphthol, conc. HCl (12 *N*), sodium nitrite and sodium hydroxide. For bleaching and dyeing of jute fabric analytical grade reagents (purity around 99%) from S. D. Fine-chem Limited, viz. hydrogen peroxide, tri-sodium phosphate, sodium hydroxide, sodium carbonate,

sodium silicate, sodium sulphate and acetic acid and non-ionic detergent (Ultravon JU, a commercial ethylene oxide condensation product of Hindusthan Ciba-Geigy Ltd.) were used.

Table 1. IR band characterization of synthesized azo dyes

Dye	Frequency (cm ⁻¹)	Characteristic group
2-Nitro-2',4'-dihydroxyazobenzene (I)	3517.9	Aromatic O-H
	1606.6	Aromatic -N=N-
	1490.9	Aromatic -NO ₂
4-Nitro-2',4'-dihydroxyazobenzene (II)	3377.1	Aromatic O-H
	1591.2	Aromatic -N=N-
	1506.3	Aromatic -NO ₂
2-Carboxy-2'-hydroxyazonaphthol (III)	3400.0	Aromatic O-H
	3035.7	Aromatic C-H
	1618.2	Aromatic -N=N-
	1595.0	Aromatic COOH γ_{O-H} (sym.)
	1392.5	Aromatic COOH γ_{O-H} (asym.)

Preparation of 2-nitro-2',4'-dihydroxyazobenzene² (I) :

2-Nitroaniline (4 g) was dissolved in 100 ml of (0.5 *N*) HCl. The solution (pH 2–3) was cooled in a freezing mixture and diazotized by dropwise addition of cooled (0 °C) saturated solution of sodium nitrite (3 g), pH 4–5. The diazotized product thus formed was added slowly to a cooled (0 to 5 °C) alkaline solution of resorcinol (2.65 g). The resultant mixture was acidified with (2 *N*) HCl when a brilliant red dye was obtained. It was filtered through suction, washed thoroughly with double distilled water till free from acid. The yield of dye was 4.8 g showing 82% conversion.

Preparation of 4-nitro-2',4'-dihydroxyazobenzene (II) :

The method of preparation of dye I was repeated for preparation of dye II using the substrate 4-nitroaniline (4 g) in 0.5 (*N*) HCl solution (pH 1–2) which was diazotized with sodium nitrite (3 g) followed by reaction with alkaline solution of resorcinol (2.65 g) at low temperature (0–5 °C). The yield of dye was 4.7 g showing 80% conversion.

Preparation of 2-carboxy-2'-hydroxyazonaphthol (III) :

Anthranilic acid (0.3 g) was dissolved in 50 ml of dilute HCl solution containing 12.5 ml of conc. HCl. The solution (pH 2–3) was cooled in a freezing mixture and diazotised with dropwise addition of cooled solution (0 °C) of sodium nitrite (3.25 g). Keeping the temperature at (0–5 °C), the diazotised product thus formed was added slowly to a cooled (0–5 °C) alkaline solution of β -naphthol (0.35 g). The resultant mixture was acidified with 2 (*N*) HCl when a brilliant orange dye was obtained. It was filtered through suction, washed thoroughly with double distilled water till free from acid. The yield of dye was 0.5 g showing 78% conversion.

Bleaching of jute fabric :

Conventional bleaching of grey jute fabric was performed in a closed vessel containing hydrogen peroxide (2 vol), trisodium phosphate (5 g/L), sodium hydroxide (1 g/L), sodium silicate (10 g/L) and nonionic detergent, Ultravon JU (2 ml/L) for 2 h at 90 °C with a material to liquor ratio 1 : 20. The pH of the bath was maintained at 10. After bleaching, the fibre samples were washed thoroughly in cold water, neutralised with acetic acid (2 ml/L), washed again in cold water and finally dried.

Dyeing of bleached jute fabric :

Bleached jute fabric samples were dyed with the three azo dyes containing azo group as chromophore and nitro, carboxy and hydroxyl groups as auxochrome, by direct dyeing process. The dye was first converted to sodium salt for solubilisation and the solubilised dye was then applied to fabric by direct dyeing process.

Pasting and solubilisation : Dye (4%, owf) was pasted with a little Ultravon JU and warm water. Sodium carbonate (half the weight of the dye) was added to the paste, then added hot water to make the volume 100 ml. The dye solution (pH 9–10) was heated for 10 min at 80 °C.

Dyeing : Dye bath was made with the dissolved dye (4% owf), sodium hydroxide (1 gpl) and sodium sulphate (5 gpl) and the material to liquor ratio was kept at 1 : 20. The bleached jute fabric sample was dipped into the dye bath, temperature slowly increased to 80 °C and dyeing was continued at that temperature for one hour. Thereafter, the sample was washed thoroughly with cold water, soaped with Ultravon JU (2 gpl) in a bath containing water (material to liquor ratio, 1 : 20) at 50 °C for 15 min followed by washing thoroughly with cold water and drying in air.

Determination of physico-chemical properties : All dyed jute fabric samples were subjected to wash fastness test in a Launder-o-Meter as specified in IS : 3361-1979³. The wash fastness rating of all dyed jute fabric samples were evaluated with a computerized colour matching system.

The Spectrascan-5100^R computerized colour matching system was used to measure the λ_{max} , reflectance and *K/S* values of dyed jute fabric samples using the following formula

$$K/S = [(1 - R)2R] \propto C$$

where *K*, the coefficient of absorption, *S* the coefficient of scattering, *R* the reflectance of substrate at λ_{max} and *C* concentration of dye. The *K/S* value is an index of dye uptake.

Infra-red spectra : The infra-red spectra of the dyes I, II and III were recorded over a range 4000–400 cm⁻¹ on a Jasco-4200 FT-IR spectrometer making KBr pellets of the three dyes.

Table 2. Performance of synthesized azo dyes on bleached jute fabric

Dye sample	λ_{\max} of the dye solution (nm)	Dye exhaustion (%)	λ_{\max} of the dyed fabric (nm)	K/S value	Reflectance (%)	Wash fastness
2-Nitro-2',4'-dihydroxyazobenzene (I)	456.7	22	470	5.88	7.29	3-4
4-Nitro-2',4'-dihydroxyazobenzene (II)	451	42	470	6.99	6.28	3
2-Carboxy-2'-hydroxyazonaphthol (III)	485	8	490	4.89	10.33	2-3

Results and discussion

Structural elucidation of dyes :

Dye I (2-Nitro-2',4'-dihydroxyazobenzene)²: The azo dye was synthesized by diazotization of *o*-nitroaniline followed by coupling with alkaline solution of resorcinol. The elemental analysis data found : (calcd.) : C, 55.56 (55.59); H, 3.49 (3.47); N, 16.17 (16.22).

Dye II (4-Nitro-2',4'-dihydroxyazobenzene): The azo dye was synthesized by diazotization of *p*-nitroaniline followed by coupling with alkaline solution of resorcinol. The elemental analysis data found : (calcd.) : C, 55.56 (55.59); H, 3.44 (3.47); N, 16.18 (16.22).

Dye III (2-Carboxy-2'-hydroxyazonaphthol): The azo dye was synthesized by diazotization of anthranilic acid followed by coupling with alkaline solution of β -naphthol. The elemental analysis data found : (calcd.) : C, 68.53 (68.57); H, 4.29 (4.26); N, 10.00 (9.95).

The band characterization⁴ of the three dyes by FT-IR spectrometer is reported in Table 1. All the dyes were found to contain azo group and characteristic hydroxyl and nitro groups respectively from their infra-red bands.

The dyes I, II and III were partially soluble in water but completely soluble in alkaline medium (pH 9-10). All three dyes have azo group as chromophore, dye I and II have two hydroxyl groups and a nitro group as auxochrome and dye III has carboxy and hydroxy groups as auxochrome. Due to the presence of the chromophore and auxochrome groups, the compounds have affinity towards the jute fibre and can be treated as dyes for textile application. The performance of the dyes I, II and III applied to the jute fabric is reported in Table 2.

Due to different chemical structure of three dyes, their λ_{\max} and dye exhaustion vary significantly. There is small difference of λ_{\max} value for dye solution and dyed fabric as the bleached jute fabric i.e. substrate has some influence on the λ_{\max} of the dyed fabric. Colour yields of the dyed fabric

which is measured by K/S value shows a direct relationship with the dye exhaustion (%). As the exhaustion (%) is low in the dye III colour yield is also low. Wash fastness is good in case of dye I and dye II but moderate in case of dye III. It may be due to presence of two hydroxy groups in the first two dyes, which produce better exhaustion and colour yield in the dyed jute fabric.

The dyes synthesized in the experiment resemble well with the similar commercial product Chlorantine Fast Orange TGLI (CI Direct Orange dye, constitution no. 40215), a direct class of dye produced by Hindusthan Ciba-Geigy Ltd.

The dye (λ_{\max} 450 nm) was applied on jute fabric in alkaline bath¹. The dyed fabric showed good colour strength (K/S value, 12.83) and wash fastness property of grade 3.

Conclusion :

The synthesized dyes contain azo group as chromophore and carboxy and hydroxy groups in dye III and two hydroxy and nitro groups as auxochrome in dyes I and II respectively. The dyes can be applied for dyeing jute fabric in basic condition. The investigation reveals that the performance of dyes is satisfactory and they may find application in jute dyeing.

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